

PRESCHOOL EDUCATION CLUSTER: COOPERATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: The article deals with the issues of cooperation between a higher educational institution and pre-school educational organizations on the basis of a cluster of preschool education. The author also expressed his opinion and feedback on the methodology of cooperation in the search for optimal ways to form solidarity of pre-school educational organizations and higher educational institutions.

Keywords: Preschool education cluster, solidarity, effective methods, methodology, result, customer, guarantee.

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There are many scientific works devoted to the interaction of the organization of preschool education and the higher education system at different levels (preschool, higher education) (for example, A. Belyaeva; Kustova Yu.A., Shubert Yu.F. and Kozlov A.V.; Matrosova P. G. and others). These studies present research results on various aspects of cooperation. Therefore, taking into account the trends in the development of the preschool education system, it is important to develop theoretical and methodological issues that ensure effective cooperation between PEO and higher education institutions.

On the one hand, preschool education system as a subject of society serves as the center of science, culture and education. The leading place in this system is given to universities. On the other hand, the higher education system is an economic entity. It uses state resources to fulfill state orders for personnel training and is a guarantee of technical development of the national economy.

We name the main rules of the higher education system:

- the final consumer of the results of the state education system (this customer forms his requirements for the final product of the education system and evaluates them in terms of satisfying his interests);

- the central element (subject) of the educational system is a person who participates as a carrier (representative) of the result of the practical activity of the educational system. Therefore, all the activities of the educational system (by making him an employee required by society and the state) are directed to the last element;

- each person, due to a number of circumstances, has a personal vision of his goal, determines his place in society and achieves it by implementing certain standards of work (first of all, his practical activity): (status, status). Therefore, he is interested in the maximum value of the equivalent received for his labor and, accordingly, in increasing its quality.

- PEO (pre-school educational organizations) imposes its own requirements on the higher education system, and these requirements may not correspond to the state's requirements on the higher education system. At the same time, a question arises regarding the priority requirements for the higher education system.

Consequently, the higher education system is in a double position: on the one hand, it must fulfill the state order, and on the other hand, it must be in the interests of everyone.

Each educational institution is unique in many ways (territory, resources, identity, image, etc.). At the same time, all educational institutions work in the external environment, which is not only formed by them, but also has an external influence on their internal life. The main factor affecting the activity of the educational institution is the market, which determines the interaction and interdependence of the educational institution with the general economic system.

Universities are producers of several types of products: educational services; scientific and technical products; educational and methodological guides. Despite being in the university's activities, as a rule, all types of these services, in the spectrum, are of decisive importance. If we consider the educational process as a type of production designed to "prepare" a specialist from an applicant, then along with the "subject of work", "tools of work" and other attributes, it is necessary to take into account the efficiency of educational technologies and the university as a whole. [63].

To optimize the activity of a professional educational institution, it is necessary to measure and evaluate not only the effectiveness of the implemented activities, but also its effectiveness. The study of scientific literature shows that the problem of evaluating the quality of postgraduate training is very complex. Without solving this problem, the main goal of the education system, the formation of the personnel potential of the state, cannot be achieved.

Experts have proposed many options for determining the "quality of education", which have their own advantages and disadvantages, but in one way or another, they reflect the essence of the described phenomenon.

It should be remembered that the concept of "quality of education" is a narrower concept compared to the quality of education. The quality of teaching is a direct result of the learning process. It depends on the level of qualifications of professors and teachers, educational and methodological support, the state of the

material and technical base, the intellectual potential of students, and others. The quality of education includes additional features, for example, the demand for graduates of educational institutions, their career level, evaluation of the university's industrial relations from the point of view of employers, and the presence or absence of complaints should also be taken into account.

Other authors interpret "Graduate quality of education" as certain knowledge and skills, mental, physical and moral development, which graduates of educational institutions have achieved in accordance with their planned goals [15].

Then the quality of education can be defined as the compliance of a graduate - a young specialist with the established standards and requirements of the labor market accepted at a certain time.

Analysis of the meanings of the existing definitions allows us to distinguish the following main features of the category "quality of education":

- compliance of the level of knowledge and skills of graduates with the established standard;
- compliance with established standards of requirements for comprehensive assessment of universities' activities;
- level of meeting the requirements of various participants of the educational process (society, state, students, employers).

The quality of education consists of the quality of the educational process - the educational service and the quality of its result - the preparation of a graduate. It manifests itself in the difference between the internal and external components of the quality of dual education.

The internal components of educational quality include:

- conditions of the educational process;
- the quality of the educational process;
- the quality of the results of the educational process;
- internal components related to pedagogy and personnel policy.

External components of educational quality include:

- compliance of education with educational requirements of students and their parents;
- compliance with state educational standards;
- image of the university as a pledge of higher education;
- compliance with the requirements of the modern labor market.

Based on the characteristics and requirements of consumers of the results of the university's educational activities, the following goals of training highly educated specialists can be distinguished:

- 1) the activity of educational institutions should consist of training specialists to the extent necessary to meet the needs of the society for labor resources;

2) the higher education system should ensure the training of qualified specialists with knowledge and skills that meet the requirements of the labor market;

3) In general, in order to ensure the effective functioning of each educational institution in the national education system, the training of highly educated specialists should be carried out at the most reasonable costs.

Achieving each of the set goals ensures efficiency, and ensures the efficiency of the entire complex - higher education system and each university. The characteristics of the higher education system determine the secondary nature of the goals: economic and social. The above-mentioned goals have a clear economic nature and determine the stability and successful operation of the national economic system.

The products of the higher educational institution are the result of educational, scientific, consulting and production work and services for citizens, organizations, as well as specialists who are graduates of the university. Based on the goals of the educational institution, its main product and result are trained specialists. In this regard, it can be argued that the content of efficiency is the quality of training of specialists, its specialization and the level of demand for it.

Young professionals from many countries of the world community lack practical experience in the labor market, and they have difficulties in adapting to real professional conditions.

Based on this, closer cooperation between higher education institutions and pre-school education organizations is necessary.

The relationship between higher education institutions and pre-school educational organizations is a very important and urgent problem. Both parties are interested in establishing close relations so that the university is aware of their ever-changing needs and can respond to them in a certain way by regulating the educational process. In turn, preschool education can influence the educational process through direct participation in organizations.

Preschool education organizations are consumers of specialists, and can also be a customer who sets the state order and imposes additional requirements on the qualities of a young specialist compared to the standard. In our opinion, additional training should be paid by pre-school educational organizations, while it includes the selection of students, the implementation of personal personnel policy, the choice of the production method (with the specific quality indicators of the organization, with the necessary economic and social indicators, product provision, labor efficiency) and social problems (increasing the standard of living of employees in accordance with internal and external conditions; etc.).

The state, university, PEO and students interact as participants in a single process to meet the demand for educational services. This interaction can be considered non-profit in the sense that it does not have the main purpose of making a profit, but on the other hand, the interaction with the effective activity of universities and PEOs can serve as an additional source of extra-budgetary income of the university.

A modern university that provides employment for graduates, meets the needs of PEOs for specific specialists, supports the scientific, technical and economic development of the country, is trying to build relations with organizations in mutually beneficial conditions.

From the point of view of the organization of mutual relations, from the point of view of the organization of relations "higher educational institution - pre-school education organization", as a result of the continuous organization of theoretical training in the educational institution by specialists in the main PEOs, as a result of the organization of the educational cluster on the basis of active mutually beneficial cooperation between the PEO and the educational institution principle.

The idea of creating a new model of interaction of education and PEO based on social partnership, cluster approach, transferring part of the management powers to social partners and responsibility for their implementation is being promoted as a leading idea.

In the conditions of the market economy, the main task of an educational institution in close cooperation with employers - providing the labor market with the necessary personnel and quality specialists - can be effectively implemented in the research.

The results of the research were tested during the creation, operation and development of an educational cluster on the basis of the Institute of Pre-School Education System Staff Training and Retraining.

The essence of convergence is that it means the processes of interaction of different objects, their mutual conditionality, change of state, mutual transition, as well as the transfer of one object to another. Interaction is a direct or indirect, external or internal relationship, communication. The concept of integrity is closely related to the concept of structure. Cohesion is a unifying factor, through which parts are united into a certain type of wholeness [87]. Correlation determines the interdependence of cause and effect: each of the interacting parties acts as a result of the cause of the other and simultaneously as a result of the opposite effect of the opposite party. Dependency determines the development of objects. It is the interaction of opposites, the contradiction, that is, the deepest source, basis and ultimate cause of the emergence, self-movement and development of objects.

Below we will name the main features of cohabitation.

The first key characteristic of the interacting parties in any collaborative process is activity.

Consistency is the basis and condition for establishing various relations between objects, including the connection between cause and effect. This is the basis of any system, which includes the connection (in the form of interaction) of its elements, components. Accordingly, systematicity is its second main feature as a demonstration of the commonality of objects in all relationships and relations.

The search for optimal methods of forming the solidarity of pre-school educational establishments and higher education institutions requires the development of a system of concepts that forms the basis of the solidarity methodology [28].

Conceptual component, as a rule, is an integral set of concepts. One of the important concepts is the concept of "approach". In the field of pedagogy, the concept of "approach" is widespread. Many scholars claim that the approach is a comprehensive pedagogical tool that includes three main components:

- basic concepts used in the process of learning, managing and changing educational practices;
- principles as a starting point or basic rules for the implementation of educational activities;
- methods and methods of forming the educational and educational process.

Summarizing the opinions of various scientists, we emphasize that the approach to pedagogy serves as a methodological principle, on the basis of which the study of a particular pedagogical problem is carried out. Based on the essence of the concept of cooperation, we can say that the formation of interaction can take place on the basis of a systematic approach.

A systematic approach is a general scientific method of analyzing any studied pedagogical phenomenon, which is primarily "based on the understanding of objects as a system" [80].

The essence of the systematic approach as a general scientific method of analyzing all the factors affecting the studied phenomenon, which must be taken into account before making a decision, has been determined in the research of a number of scientists.

The main conceptual apparatus of systems research I.V. Blauberg, E.G. It is given in the works of Yudin and other scientists. From the analysis of their work, it follows that the system appears as a set of interrelated elements that have integrative properties and laws, forming a stable unity and integrity.

In the development of a systematic approach to the analysis of pedagogical phenomena, B.S. Gershunsky, T.A. Ilina, F.F. Korolev and other scientists participated [26].

Researchers I.V. Blauberg and E.K. According to Yudin, the methodological apparatus of the systematic approach is internally ordered and unified due to its universality, which opens up great opportunities for studying the observed objects. Thus, the study of the interaction formation process can be carried out within the framework of a systematic approach [13]. The systematic approach allows to identify and systematize the relations that arise in the process of cooperation, to organize the knowledge and information distributed in this process. The use of a systematic approach involves the use of special concepts and methods, adherence to certain principles. The main concept of this approach is "system".

The term "system" is a final generalization that emphasizes the aspect of reality that the observer is interested in at the moment, and this concept has many definitions. In pedagogy, in many cases, a system is defined as a set of elements that are connected to each other as a whole, capable of changing its state and having properties that differ from the properties of the elements that make up the system. In this definition, an element is the simplest integral part of the studied object that performs these functions. The internal state of such an element quantitatively describes the properties of the real object.

Any definition or specification of the system definition requires the definition of the variable properties of the external environment, the set of objects affecting the system, as well as the definition of the objects that change as a result of the behavior of the system.

In addition, when considering the object as a system, a number of properties are emphasized in it. The first is object integrity. Any object or many objects can be called a system if the general review is based on some point of view and helps to answer the researcher's question and solve the problem. Regularly changing the properties of an object and its parameters is based on a system process. Secondly, the existence of a learning goal is a criterion that determines the existence of a given object as a whole. Thirdly, the object under consideration is defined as a subsystem, a part of some larger system, where the subsystem is defined as a group of elements selected from the unified system based on some characteristic. Fourth, the studied object itself, in turn, is divided into subsystems, i.e. It is characterized by structure, which means certain and relatively stable relations between its elements and subsystems.

The second component of the systems approach is the principles, that is, the initial and basic rules for knowing and changing system objects.

The principle of integrity. It is called the first one, because integrity, which is considered the main criterion for classifying an object as a group of systems, and the process of cognitive or practical activity as a system.

Communication (communicative) principle. It is not for nothing that scientists emphasize that knowing the system first of all means studying its relations - internal and external relations.

The principle of composition. Due to the stability of the structures, the integrity of the system and the interaction of its components are ensured. In addition to stability (relative, of course), the structure also has qualities such as mobility and change. Many scientists relate these features of the structure with the possibilities of system change and the emergence of a new integrated (system) quality.

The principle of control and concentration. Purpose and management should be considered not only as the most important elements of social systems, but also as system-forming factors of their operation and development.

The principle of development. The development of the system is defined in science as the process of quantitative and qualitative changes that determine the formation of its new integrative features and the transition from one level of integrity to another. A systematic approach to cooperation between educational institutions and customer-employees requires considering it as a complex social dynamic system [51]. Considering that PEO and educational institution are systems of social activity, we can determine their internal structure (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Cooperation between a higher education institution and a preschool education organization.

subjects of activity for higher education - pedagogues and students; for PEO - educators-pedagogues and specialists);

means of activity (for an educational institution - teaching means: methodical, training manuals, tools, TCO, etc.; for PEO - technology means of training: machines, tools, devices, etc.);

subjects of activity (for an educational institution - educational materials, educational content; for an enterprise - raw materials, materials, components, etc.);

activity technology (for an educational institution - educational technology; for PEO - professional development technology).

The mutual cooperation of the educational institution and the enterprise gives important features to all elements of the system of professional training of specialists (subjects of the educational process, educational manuals, structural and educational technologies). At the same time, teaching technologies are changing, they have the characteristics of flexible intensive training of specialists with targeted distribution of graduates to pre-school educational establishments. Educational programs for professions and specialties take into account the specific characteristics of the organizations where specialists are trained.

The educational institution has the ability to quickly change the composition of specialist personnel training, qualification characteristics (professional standards), educational standards, based on them, by developing curricula and training programs in accordance with the needs and conditions of interested PEOs. To achieve these goals, the required number of study hours are allocated from the reserve fund in various courses.

Leading specialists of preschool education organizations are involved in studying special courses on modern advanced technological processes, technological equipment, teaching subjects in new scientific and technical directions, the results of which are planned to be used in PEO. It is an important task to provide the material and technical base necessary for the training of specialists.

Creation of joint educational, scientific and production units on the basis of cooperation - establishment of branches of educational institutions and departments in enterprises, technological parks and other structures.

An important component of the relationship between the educational institution and the enterprise and the possibility of providing internships for the engineering and teaching staff of the educational institution to the problems and needs of a particular enterprise, and the possibility of carrying out term jobs and

diploma projects in the enterprise with the subsequent employment of graduates should be the focus of training.

A systematic approach to the process of establishing relationships is manifested in considering it as a model with integrity consisting of several blocks.

Modeling in the scientific field is understood as a theoretical method of scientific knowledge, which is described as the reproduction of the properties of an object in another object created specifically for its study. The second of the objects, called the model, is in a certain objective correspondence with a certain object, is able to replace it at certain stages of cognition and give it during learning, ultimately, it provides information about the modeled object itself [11]. Modeling can be the following: first, a cognitive process that includes processing information about events from the external environment, in which images corresponding to objects, mental models appear in the mind; secondly, the process of building a certain model in the form of an object - a substitute that is related to the original object in a certain similarity relationship.

Modeling includes the following steps: preliminary analysis of the process or educational subject (original); construction and further study of this original model; transferring the received data to the educational process or object (original); analysis of model reliability and efficiency [81]. Modeling is a circular process. This means that after finishing one model of one construction cycle, it is possible and sometimes necessary to do a second, then a third, etc. At the same time, the knowledge about the studied object expands and improves, and the model of the object is gradually improved.

Thus, the modeling method is the creation of an ideal organizational model from the point of view of scientific data and the conditions for the operation of the pedagogical process or part of it. Modeling can occur in the process of learning and experimenting with certain pedagogical forms, working methods, their interactions with each other, organizing large-scale research.

A systematic approach and the method of modeling complex phenomena provide the opportunity for multi-faceted research of any object. Choosing any system as a modeling object requires the following: the existence of some original object consisting of many elements; the presence of an observer-researcher; statement of the problem, defining the boundaries of the modeling object for the observer, highlighting its important features. At the same time, a system of representations was developed in the form of drawings, graphs, schemes, mechanisms, that is, a model was built that plays the role of an abstract or substitute for the object under consideration.

We consider the definition of the pedagogical model to be important among the definitions we have taken as a basis. I.M. Remorenko stated: "Pedagogical

model is a generalized, abstract-logical image of a specific phenomenon of the pedagogical system, which reflects and reflects the structural and functional relationships of the object of pedagogical research, presented in the necessary visual form and capable of providing new knowledge about the object of learning" [69].

The pedagogical model (according to Trubina L.N.) performs the following functions: an ideal or working model for the interaction of participants in the educational process; comparison, a sample to determine the correctness of the selected forms, means and methods of this interaction; to demonstrate the content, organization and development of the educational process; checking the correctness and completeness of theoretical and practical creative knowledge and skills.

By the model we mean the representation of the studied object in a form different from its actual existence, in a form in which its study gives new knowledge about it. According to many scientists (V.A. Mikheev, V.A. Shtof, etc.), the model does not reflect all the properties of the real object, it is only necessary for learning the task [88].

An example of this is the target model of the project on the management of the training of specialists, ensuring the integration of the educational institution with PEO and scientific organizations, as well as the improvement and development of the socio-economic and organizational mechanisms of the training of specialists.

The main factors of the management structure for the training of specialists based on the mutual cooperation of the educational institution and PEOs should be the final results and socio-economic functions.

The analysis of the main goals and functions of management focused on final results and integration processes in the training of preschool education specialists and socio-economic mechanisms of system activity shows that the implementation of design-purpose structures is particularly suitable for production requirements. The advantages of such structures are that they do not disrupt existing relationships in higher education institutions and pre-school education organizations, and allow for the creation of a flexible organizational structure aimed at quickly solving the problems of training specialists by the educational institution and PEOs with the help of internal mechanisms.

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